

Hope and Self-efficacy as Determinants of Employee Engagement and Job Satisfaction among Banking Professionals

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The current research investigated how self-efficacy and hope influence work engagement and job satisfaction among professionals working in the banking sector. In the modern banking sector, employees face high work pressure, demanding targets, and continuous customer interaction, making psychological strengths important for positive work outcomes. The study comprises a sample of 300 banking professionals from public and private sector banks in Bihar. Psychological Capital Questionnaire (Luthans et al., 2006), Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (Schaufeli et al., 2002), and Job Satisfaction Survey (Spector, 1985) were used for the assessment. Correlation and regression techniques were used to examine the collected data. The results indicated that all the variables were significantly and positively associated with each other. Self-efficacy positively predicted work engagement and job satisfaction, indicating that employees with greater confidence in their abilities experience higher enthusiasm and satisfaction at work. Hope also showed a positive influence on both work engagement and job satisfaction. The findings advocate that positive psychological resource development among employees can promote greater well-being, higher motivation, and improved effectiveness within organizations.

Keywords: Self-efficacy, hope, work engagement, job satisfaction and workplace

With the emergence of Positive Psychology, greater emphasis has been placed on the study of human strengths, positive emotions, and psychological resources that improve individual well-being and organizational effectiveness (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). In the modern organizational environment, employees frequently experience occupational stress, excessive workload, competition, and performance pressure, which may negatively influence their work engagement and job satisfaction (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). Therefore, organizations are increasingly focusing on positive psychological capacities that help employees remain motivated, adaptable, and productive in challenging situations (Luthans, 2002). Among these psychological resources, self-efficacy and hope have gained considerable importance in positive organizational behaviour. Personnel with higher self-efficacy tend to demonstrate greater confidence, persistence, and problem-solving abilities at the workplace (Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998). Similarly, Employees with higher levels of hope tend to demonstrate greater work engagement, stronger motivation, and increased job satisfaction (Avey, Luthans, & Jensen, 2009).

Hope

Hope is considered a positive motivational state that helps individuals achieve goals through determination and effective planning. It involves both the determination to achieve goals and the capacity to develop effective routes for reaching them (Snyder, 2002). Agency represents a person's motivational drive and confidence toward goal achievement, while pathways refer to the methods and plans created to accomplish those goals (Snyder, 2002). Individuals with high levels of hope are generally more persistent, confident, and capable of overcoming obstacles during stressful situations (Snyder, Rand, & Sigmon, 2002). Hope also contributes to psychological well-being, optimism, and life satisfaction (Lopez, Snyder, & Pedrotti, 2003). Hope plays an important role in improving employee motivation, work performance, and adaptability. Workforces with higher hope are found to be better able to manage workplace stress, organizational change, and professional challenges effectively (Luthans, Youssef, & Avolio, 2007). Hopeful employees also demonstrate higher work engagement, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment (Peterson & Byron, 2008). Furthermore, hope positively influences resilience, productivity, and positive organizational behavior among employees (Avey, Reichard, Luthans, & Mhatre, 2011).

Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy is defined as a person's confidence in their capability to successfully complete tasks and attain specific goals. This concept was proposed by Bandura (1977) as an important element of Social Cognitive Theory. Bandura explained that self-efficacy affects the way individuals think, feel, motivate themselves, and respond to various situations. People with higher self-efficacy usually display stronger confidence, determination, and effective problem-solving skills, while those with low self-efficacy are likely to witness uncertainty, fear, and anxiety when facing difficult circumstances.

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Self-efficacy plays an important role in determining human behavior, emotional functioning, and performance. It helps individuals to deal efficiently and resourcefully with demanding situations and maintain psychological stability (Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995). Research has also shown that self-efficacy contributes significantly to motivation, achievement, and goal attainment (Schunk, 1991). In workplace environments, employees possessing strong self-efficacy are inclined to be motivated, flexible, and actively involved in their job responsibilities. Therefore, self-efficacy is considered an important psychological resource for enhancing employee well-being and workplace outcomes.

Work Engagement

Work engagement describes the extent to which employees are psychologically connected to and actively involved in their work. Kahn (1990) explained work engagement as a condition in which individuals devote their emotional, mental, and physical efforts to their professional roles. Later, researchers characterized it as a positive and satisfying state related to work, marked by energy, commitment, and deep concentration (Schaufeli et al., 2002). The concept of work engagement is generally understood through three major dimensions: (i) vigor that represents high energy, persistence, and mental strength while performing work tasks, (ii) dedication which reflects a strong sense of enthusiasm, inspiration, and pride toward one's job and (iii) absorption refers to complete focus and deep involvement in work activities, where employees become fully immersed in what they are doing (Schaufeli et al., 2004). Research has shown that engaged employees are more energetic, motivated, productive, and psychologically connected with their work, which positively influences organizational growth and performance (Bakker et al., 2016). Studies have also indicated that proactive behaviors such as job crafting help employees increase job resources and challenging work aspects, which further enhance work engagement (Tims et al., 2012; Petrou et al., 2012).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction reflects the extent to which employees hold favorable or unfavorable attitudes and emotions regarding their job and work experiences. It is considered a favorable emotional response that develops from the evaluation of job characteristics and work experiences (Robbins & Judge, 2014). Job satisfaction is influenced by psychological, physical, and environmental factors that contribute to an employee's sense of fulfillment and well-being at their place of work (Spector, 1997). Employees with high job satisfaction generally demonstrate positive attitudes toward their jobs, whereas dissatisfied employees may develop negative attitudes and reduced motivation (Locke, 1976). Research has shown that low job satisfaction can negatively affect organizational outcomes by reducing productivity, commitment, and employee retention (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007; De Beer, Rothmann, & Pienaar, 2012). Studies also suggest that practices such as job crafting help employees improve work engagement, resilience, and job satisfaction by adjusting job demands and available resources in line with their skills, needs, and personal objectives (Tims et al., 2012). Therefore, job satisfaction is considered an important factor for employee well-being and organizational effectiveness.

Review of Literature

Relationships between Self-efficacy and Outcomes

In organizational environments, self-efficacy is widely recognized as a significant factor influencing both work engagement and job satisfaction. It represents an individual's assurance about their ability to successfully handle tasks and responsibilities (Bandura, 1997). Employees with stronger self-efficacy are generally more confident, persistent, and motivated while executing their duties (Bandura, 1997). Work engagement is positively influenced by self-efficacy because confident employees demonstrate, i.e., higher vigor, ii. dedication, and iii. absorption in work activities (Luthans, 2002). Personal resources such as self-efficacy also enhance employee engagement and performance (Xanthopoulou, Bakker, Demerouti, & Schaufeli, 2007). Bakker and Demerouti (2008) found that self-efficacy helps employees cope effectively with job demands and workplace stress. Many studies have also found a positive association between self-efficacy and job satisfaction. Employees who possess higher self-efficacy tend to feel more satisfied with their jobs, as they perceive themselves to be more effective, skilled, and capable in executing their tasks (Judge & Bono, 2001). Positive psychological resources such as self-efficacy improve workplace well-being and satisfaction (Luthans, Youssef, & Avolio, 2007). Higher self-efficacy also increases organizational commitment and motivation among employees (Staples, Hulland, & Higgins, 1999).

Relationships between Hope and Outcomes

Hope is considered an important psychological resource that predicts work engagement and job satisfaction in organizational settings. Hope is defined as the positive motivational condition in which individuals possess both the determination to pursue goals and the skills to identify effective ways to achieve them (Snyder, 2002). Personnel with higher hope are generally more confident, motivated, and persistent in handling workplace challenges and achieving organizational objectives (Snyder, Rand, & Sigmon, 2002). Several researchers demonstrated that hope positively predicts work engagement. Higher hope among employees shows a greater vigor, dedication, and absorption in their work activities (Luthans, Youssef, & Avolio, 2007). Hopeful employees are also more adaptable and capable of coping effectively with occupational stress and organizational change (Youssef & Luthans, 2007). Research by Sweetman and Luthans (2010) suggested that hope enhances positive organizational behavior and increases employee engagement. Hope also has a positive relationship with job satisfaction. Higher levels of hope lead to experiencing greater satisfaction among employees because they feel more optimistic and capable of achieving work-related goals (Peterson & Byron, 2008). Avey, Reichard, Luthans, and Mhatre (2011) also found that hope contributes to employee well-being, motivation, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction.

Objectives of the Study

On the basis of available research literature following objectives have been proposed:

- To investigate the relationship between self- efficacy and work engagement.
- To investigate the relationships between self- efficacy and job satisfaction.

- To investigate the relationships between hope and work engagement.
- To investigate the relationships between hope and job satisfaction.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1*: Employees' self - efficacy will be positively related to work engagement.
- *H2*: Employees' self - efficacy will be positively related to job satisfaction.
- *H3*: Employees' hope will be positively related to work engagement.
- *H4*: Employees hope will be positively related to job satisfaction.

Method

Participants

The present study included banking professionals employed in various public and private sector banks across Bihar. A total of 300 participants were selected for the research, of which 48% belonged to public sector banks and 52% were employed in private sector banks. Different demographic variables were considered in the study. The participants' ages ranged from 30 to 60 years, with 26.3% belonging to the 30-37 age group, 23.7% to the 38-45 age group, 27.3% to the 46-53 age group, and 22.7% aged 54 years and above. The mean for the age was 45.12 years ($SD = 11.42$). Regarding gender distribution, 51.3% of the respondents were male and 48.7% were female. Most participants were married 88.3% while 11.7% were single. In terms of educational qualifications, 53.3% had completed graduation and 39.7% held postgraduate degrees, whereas 7.0% reported other qualifications. Regarding occupation, 31.7% were assistant managers, 27.3% were clerical staff, 21.0% were field officers, and 20.0% were branch managers. With respect to monthly income, 38.0% earned between ₹51,000 and ₹60,000, 27.3% earned ₹50,000 or below, 20.7% earned between ₹61,000 and ₹70,000 and 14.0% reported incomes of ₹71,000 or above. Employees having a minimum of five years of work experience were included as participants in the study.

Measures

Psychological Capital Questionnaire (PCQ-24): Hope and self-efficacy were assessed through the Psychological Capital Questionnaire (PCQ-24) developed by Luthans et al. (2007). 6 items from subscale measuring hope and 6 items measuring self-efficacy were utilized in the study. Participants provided their responses using a 6-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 6 (*strongly agree*). The Cronbach's alpha of hope and self-efficacy subscales were .76 and .77 respectively.

Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES): Work engagement was measured using the 17-item Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES) (Schaufeli et al., 2002), assessing vigor, dedication, and absorption. The scale demonstrated good reliability ($\alpha = .80.90$).

Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS): Job satisfaction was assessed using the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) (Spector, 1985), consisting of 36 items measuring various dimensions of job satisfaction. The scale demonstrated high reliability ($\alpha = .89$).

Procedure

This study employed a quantitative correlational research design. Simple random sampling was followed for data collection to ensure

the representativeness of the sample. Higher authorities of the banks were approached to facilitate this process. Participants were given an information sheet summarizing the aims of the research and including the contact details of the researcher. It was mentioned that the participation is voluntary. The confidentiality and anonymity of responses were assured. Data were collected through standardized questionnaires measuring hope, self- efficacy, work engagement, and job satisfaction, along with demographic information. Respondents filled their responses during the office hour when convenient to them. It took 10 minutes to complete a set of questionnaires.

Statistical Analyses

Data collected from banking professionals of public and private sector banks were pooled and analyzed using SPSS version 27. Initially, descriptive statistics along with correlation coefficients were computed to examine the relationships among self-efficacy, Hope, work engagement and job satisfaction. Further, linear regression analyses were conducted to assess the predictive role of job crafting, self-efficacy and hope on work engagement and job satisfaction.

Table 1

Showed that Self-efficacy, Hope, Work Engagement, and Job Satisfaction

Variables	Work Engagement	Job satisfaction
Self-Efficacy	.554**	.540**
Hope	.547**	.615**

Note. ** $p < .01$ level

The findings showed that self-efficacy, hope, work engagement, and job satisfaction were significantly and positively associated at the .01 level of significance ($p < .01$).

This suggests that higher levels of personal and job-related resources are associated with better psychological health and greater work engagement among the respondents.

Table 2

Results of Linear Regression Analysis with Self-efficacy as the Predictor Variable and Work Engagement as the Criterion Variable

Variable	B	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Self-efficacy → work engagement	.554	.307	.305	131.992	.000

Note. ** $p < .01$ level

Table 2 indicates that self-efficacy significantly and positively predicted work engagement ($\beta = .554, p < .01$). The regression model accounted for 30.7% of the variance in work engagement ($R^2 = .307$), suggesting that employees with stronger self-efficacy tend to display greater confidence, higher energy levels, and increased involvement in their work activities. Hence, the H1 was supported.

Table 3

Results of Linear Regression Analysis with Self-efficacy as the Predictor Variable and Job Satisfaction as the Criterion Variable

Variable	B	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Self-efficacy → work engagement	.540	.292	.290	122.922	.000

Note. ** $p < .01$ level

Table 4

Results of Linear Regression Analysis with Self-efficacy as the Predictor Variable and Work Engagement as the Criterion Variable

Variable	B	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Hope → work engagement	.547	.299	.297	127.349	.000

Note. ** $p < .01$ level

Table 4 indicates that hope significantly and positively predicted work engagement ($\beta = .547, p < .01$). The regression model accounted for 29.9% of the total variance in work engagement ($R^2 = .299$), indicating that employees with higher levels of hope are more enthusiastic, motivated, and actively involved in their work. Hence, hypothesis 3 was supported.

Table 5

Regression Analysis Examining Hope as the Predictor Variable and Job Satisfaction as the Criterion Variable

Variable	B	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Hope → job satisfaction	.615	.378	.376	180.976	.000

Note. ** $p < .01$ level

The regression analysis revealed that hope significantly and positively influenced job satisfaction ($\beta = .615, p < .01$). The findings showed that hope contributed to 37.8% of the variance in job satisfaction ($R^2 = .378$), suggesting that employees with higher hopefulness tend to experience positive feelings and satisfaction toward their work. Therefore, hypothesis 4 was supported.

Discussion

The present study examined the relationship of self-efficacy and hope with work engagement and job satisfaction among employees. The findings revealed significant positive relationships among all the study variables. Self-efficacy was positively correlated with work engagement ($r = .554, p < .01$) and job satisfaction ($r = .540, p < .01$), while hope was positively correlated with work engagement ($r = .547, p < .01$) and job satisfaction ($r = .615, p < .01$). These findings indicate that employees with higher psychological resources tend to demonstrate greater engagement and satisfaction in their work.

Self-efficacy and Work Engagement

The results showed that self-efficacy significantly and positively predicted work engagement ($\beta = .554, R^2 = .307, p < .01$). This indicates that self-efficacy explained 30.7% of the variance in work engagement. Employees with strong confidence in their abilities are more likely to display enthusiasm, persistence, and dedication toward their work. These findings are consistent with previous studies indicating that self-efficacy positively enhances employee engagement and performance (Luthans et al., 2007). Similarly, Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) reported that personal resources such as self-efficacy significantly and positively contributes to work engagement.

Self-efficacy and Job Satisfaction

The findings also indicated that self-efficacy significantly predicted job satisfaction ($\beta = .540, R^2 = .292, p < .01$). The regression model showed that self-efficacy contributed to 29.2% of the variance in job satisfaction. Employees with stronger beliefs in their competencies tend to experience greater achievement and positive attitudes toward

their work. These findings support Bandura's (1997) view that self-efficacy influences motivation and occupational success. Similar findings were reported by Judge and Bono (2001), who found a positive association between self-efficacy and job satisfaction.

Hope and Work Engagement

The study further revealed that hope significantly and positively predicted work engagement ($\beta = .547, R^2 = .299, p < .01$), explaining 29.9% of the variance in work engagement. Employees with higher levels of hope are generally more motivated, optimistic, and determined to achieve organizational goals. These findings are supported by Snyder et al. (1991) who suggested that hope promotes goal-directed thinking and positive motivation. Likewise, Luthans et al. (2007) found that hopeful employees exhibit greater work engagement and organizational effectiveness.

Hope and Job Satisfaction

The results demonstrated that hope significantly influenced job satisfaction ($\beta = .615, R^2 = .378, p < .01$). Hope explained 37.8% of the variance in job satisfaction, indicating a strong predictive relationship. Employees with high hopefulness tend to maintain positive expectations regarding future outcomes and feel more satisfied with their professional roles. These findings are consistent with previous studies showing that hope positively contributes to employee satisfaction and workplace effectiveness (Luthans et al., 2007). Similarly, Youssef and Luthans (2007) reported that hope significantly predicts employee satisfaction, commitment, and happiness at work.

Limitations and Future Recommendations

Despite its important findings, the present study has some limitations. The sample size was limited and self-report questionnaires were used to collect the data, which may influence the accuracy of responses. In addition, the study used a cross-sectional design, which restricts the interpretation of cause-and-effect relationships among the variables. Future research should include larger samples from different occupational sectors to expand the external validity of the findings. Researchers may also examine other positive psychological factors such as resilience, optimism, and emotional intelligence, along with self-efficacy and hope. Longitudinal research could offer a more comprehensive understanding of how psychological resources influence workplace outcomes over time.

Conclusion

The present study concluded that self-efficacy and hope are significant predictors of work engagement and job satisfaction. Employees with high self-efficacy and hope tend to be more confident, motivated, and optimistic, and employees who remain deeply engaged in their job responsibilities are likely to experience greater satisfaction and better overall well-being at the workplace. The results of the study emphasize that positive psychological strengths play a vital role in enhancing employee effectiveness and creating favorable organizational outcomes. Therefore, organizations should focus on developing positive psychological capacities among employees to promote healthier, more engaged, and productive work environments.

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